

The Minimum Cell as a House: ideas and forms in social housing in search of a Home

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Abstract

Throughout the last century efforts have been made in order to correspond to a high demand of housing in Europe. From the high density of the traditional city, the consequences of the Industrial Revolution or the hardships of war(s), social housing has been a laboratory of experiences that include living space, shape, volume and urban solutions. The obtained results navigate through traditional answers to the most radical experiments, but at search for the same thing: a sense of belonging sustained in the idea of the 'house' in its various demonstrations, such as shape, association, internal space and ways of use.

The present analysis tries to search within the twentieth century this 'house' in various social or subsidize experiences, according to its various restrictions, of cost and effectiveness, for example. From the single houses of a garden city to the cells of Le Corbusier's Unités d'Habitation, each present an interpretation of the traditional house in its shape and use, in a more or less obvious manner.

We will take in to account different perspectives in the formalization and use of the housing cell, starting with the inner spatial solutions used in various case-studies, from the point of view of the dweller (according to its traditions 'versus' their idealized house) and the architect (who tries to substitute tradition for efficiency, or uses tradition as a basis for modernity). After that we will approach the house as a shape or single unit, and the way that its idea was formalized as single houses or the vertical sum of individual units, always taking into account their ideological and political backgrounds.

Keywords: Minimum, house, dwelling, home.

Introduction

Among the models of social housing, since the beginning of the use of the term, there has always been the need to balance the 'wanted house' and the 'feasible house'. The boundaries defined by cost always implied a compromise between the idealized house by the tenant (maintaining its customs) or by the architect (through the idealization of new spatial solutions, new ways of living)

Definition

What is intended with this paper is how the 'house', in its more elemental shape and idea, has always been manifested in the way dwellers wanted to live, or others idealize they should. This 'house' it's its most primeval shape, as an isolated building, maybe bucolic, that raises a sense of 'ownership' (opposed to the 'shared' urban dwelling, for instance).

It might sound strange to search such 'house' in social or subsidized housing, because the main ideas that occurs are those of density or stacking where an isolated element seems impossible to recognize. But this is an idea that is possible to demystify because, in between the dweller's dream home and the architect's ideal one, that 'house' was a frequent presence in the XX century housing projects.

The House as spatial definition: use and symbol

The dialectics established among the dreamed house and the proposed one were based on many factors, among them dweller and architect, cost and idea, available space and its use or symbolism. This latest item states for the more controversial one, since there is an encounter among the dweller's ancient living ways and its desire to reproduce his ideas of another social stratum. In the architect's point of view there is a need to respond to new realities, new ways of life (idealized or not), rejecting any reference to supposed inadequate models.

Popular aspirations

In the early XX's, worker's living conditions were rather bad, as the result of overcrowded cities where the poorer families only could afford a room, or at best, part of a shared house. However, since they were coming mostly from the countryside, they 'brought' with them their ancient lifestyles, based upon '(...) big rural kitchens, centered in the fireplace¹'. However, the city brings to their knowledge new models of housing, including the bourgeois house.

Figure 1: 'Popular' kitchens

Bourgeois Ambitions

So, opposed to the rural model, synonymous of poverty, the bourgeois model becomes an aspiration, in its shape, but also because of the social (and financial) statement it symbolizes.

There was, of course, the impossibility to offer each family a bourgeois house, but the goal is kept, even if 'translated' to small spaces that intended to be a symbol rather than something really useful. After the World War I the British government creates a panel of woman advisers in order to give a female perspective to the creation of new housing types. This was a way to acknowledge their part in home management but also to recognize their efforts during the war. Their solution referred a small room by the entrance used as a space for receiving guests, for example², but it didn't had much success, since the costs an area involved were unbearable and with no 'practical uses'.

¹ Nunes, João Pedro Silva - *Lisboa, arquitectura e urbanismo à escala humana: planeamento urbano e arquitectura de habitação em Olivais Sul, Lisboa 1959-1969*, 2007, Câmara Municipal de Lisboa, ISBN: 978-972-8543-08-2

² Swenarton, M.- *Building the New Jerusalem*, HIS BRE Press, 2008, pages 46-7

It must be said, however, that there is modest investigation, among the one consulted, that tried to deal with the ‘real’ use of the space in social housing, to perceive, for instance, if those aspirations were still ‘manifested’ in common spaces. Nevertheless there were some inquiries done in order to establish the population’s ‘dream house’, especially during the Italian Neo-realism, a movement that tried to make an approach to the ‘real’ populations (as opposed to the ‘ideal’ dweller of the Modern Movement). The INA-Casa process (INA: Istituto Nazionale Assicurazione; Casa: house) included the participation of the populations in the design of their new houses (part of their salary was retained voluntarily to build them), and the surveys revealed that 25% of the dwellers wanted a dinning space in the kitchen. This ‘hided’ the intention of having the living room as the single ‘domestic public’ space, where guests where received in an always ‘tidy’ area, while the kitchen was the really everyday living area. That led to the creation on the ‘lavoro’ (‘working room’), an in-between space amidst the kitchen and the living room where housework or hobbies could be carried out.

Figure 2: Nucleo Noncello, 1964 (Giulio Brunetta, 1906-1978)

In the Portuguese experience of ‘Olivais’ in the 1960’s, near Lisbon, the INA-Casa process had a great influence in the way the building process was methodically conceived (defining local materials and construction methods easily used and done). There was a level of austerity difficult to understand nowadays, like the absence of hot water (except in the tub) in the lower rent buildings, but, as in Italy, there was the explicit intention to offer as many square meters as possible. Sergio Fernandez, a Portuguese architect, refers the Italian ‘lavoro’³ in some buildings, but there also experiences similar to the ‘laboratory-kitchen’ or in-between solutions. That is why Nuno Portas classified the whole urban intervention as ‘experimental’⁴, although in its own proposal (with Bartolomeu Costa Cabral) he chose to offer a kitchen with enough space for the house tasks (while the ‘lounge’ maintained its own dining area for special occasions).

³ Nunes, João Pedro Silva - ‘Lisboa, arquitectura e urbanismo à escala humana: planeamento urbano e arquitectura de habitação em Olivais Sul, Lisboa 1959-1969’, 2007, Câmara Municipal de Lisboa, page 137, ISBN: 978-972-8543-08-2

⁴ Idem, page 147

Figure 3: Housing building in Olivais, 1963 (Nuno Portas, 1934-... and Bartolomeu Costa Cabral, ...-...)

There was an inquiry to understand the dweller's reaction to their new homes, and there was a great deal of satisfaction, since their previous houses were, to say the least, shanty. But the internal solutions were not understood by them as a 'final proposal', as most of the dwellers adapted the existing spaces to reach their own expectations and ambitions. Sometimes the complete opposite of what the architect intended.

In the lowest rent buildings the kitchen opened to the lounge was considered intolerable, because it made impossible to keep private their house tasks. The 'modernist' hatch between the kitchen and the dining room was closed, but the most impressive change was the use of a bedroom as a 'proper dining room' (alluding to the bourgeois house), even if some of the family members had to renounce to their own privacy (by sharing their rooms or even sleeping in the living room).

Figure 4: Housing building in Olivais, category 1, 1963 (João Vasconcelos Esteves, ...-...)

Interestingly, in the higher categories of the subsidized program that consisted Olivais (and the previous Alvalade neighborhood) there was still some traces of the 'old' bourgeois house, with a maid's room with its own bathroom. Even if the external image of the building was undoubtedly Modern.

Figure 5: Housing Building in Alvalade, 1959 (nicknamed ‘Bairro das Estacas’: ‘Pole District’, because of the ‘pilotis’), with maid quarters (Ruy d’Athouguia, 1922-2004)

Proving that the shapes that manifest old habits can still be of use, this solution was mentioned as an important one for today’s households, where sons and daughters tend to stay at their parent’s house for much longer: this private ‘apartment’ would thereby be a solution for their need of independence⁵.

Plebeian Ambitions

Among the models gathered in this study, little are those who intend to make a direct reference to popular or vernacular roots, even if we can relate the Italian ‘lavoro’ with the desire to establish a ‘home’ around the ‘modern’ fire place: the kitchen. João Pedro Pena Lopes interprets this desire in a very clear way, putting the apartment’s fireplace in the kitchen, instead of the living room, keeping this space as an occasional one.

Figure 6: Housing Building in Meda, 2001 (João Pedro Pena Lopes, ...-...)

We can identify a phenomenon of transport of the ‘plebeian house’ by the future tenants. We must take into account that what a person desires is, in most situations, based upon on its own knowledge, in their own experience. The SAAL (‘Serviço de Apoio Ambulatório Local’ – ‘Local Support Service’) was a movement, as political as architectural, that intended to give people a decent home. Starting immediately after the 25th of April 1974 (when the Authoritarian Portuguese Regime ‘fell’), the idea was to promote

⁵ **Monteys, Xavier; Fuertes, Pere** – “*Casa Collage – un ensayo sobre la arquitectura de la casa*”, 4th edition, 2005, Editorial Gustavo Gili, SA, Barcelona, ISBN 84-252-1869-1

local and direct contact between architects and dwellers, which meant that the populations would participate actively in their own home's designs. In one of the inquiries a housewife demanded a stone floor for her kitchen in order to have a place to light a fire. Far from being amusing, this shows how decadent their previous life was, but also the ignorance of something as simple as a stove or even a fireplace. Therefore the desire to keep upon one's known models.

The architect's visions and predictions

Being a 'Modernist' ambition to start from a clean slate, where all the ancient housing types would be forgotten, some architects maintained for a long time the presence of the 'enfilade', where rooms with no specific use would succeed one another. Karl Ehn, in his 'Karl Marx Hof' (1926) chooses the traditional 'enfilade' in his one-bedroom apartments, while with the same 53 square meters Alexander Klein, in Bad Dürrenberg (1928) offered in his 'C2 Cell' a 2 bedroom apartment with a 'fully equipped' bathroom. The difference stands in the assumption that social housing couldn't be the mere adjustment of the bourgeois house to a smaller scale. A new Type in housing should be created in order to respond to the new needs of society, culturally and sanitarily.

Figure 7: Karl Marx Hof, 1926 (Karl Ehn, 1884 – 1957) and Bad Dürrenberg, C2 Cell, 1928, Alexander Klein (1879-1961)

Modern living

The traditional scheme of 'reception-private-service' is therefore substituted by the modern 'public-private-service' sequence, where each spacial definition had a new meaning:

Reception > Public: to 'entertain' was understood as a ritual where a visit was prepared through a special room where, for example, the family's valuables were exposed. Its use was occasional, remaining the family on a daily basis in the 'private' areas. When it becomes 'public', it still is a space where visitors had access in most occasions, but it loses its occasional status to become the household's gathering room (although still competing with the kitchen). In fact, Modern architects thought that would be illogical to try to offer 'representation' spaces when areas were so scarce.

Private > Private: in this context the house's private spaces are re-evaluated: the bedroom becomes bedrooms, plural, translating a need for privacy among the household, rather than the household and visitors or friends. The real 'revolution', however, occurs when children are separated according to their gender (creating the three bedroom house). Even if these rooms are minimum, privacy is still an important achievement, when comparing to the previous houses for the poor.

Service > Service: in the bourgeois house the service areas include a spacious kitchen, a pantry and even the maid's bedroom. In this context, 'service' included the staff, and not a mere definition of 'space'. Modernism abolished, obviously, the staff in their social housing models, and service areas became

‘practical’ ones, like a bathroom (another ‘achievement’) or a kitchen: its social aspect was denied and it was intended like a mere extension of the human body: like a laboratory to mix elements (like in the Frankfurt-kitchen, by Ernst May and Grete Schütte-Lihotsky).

Figure 8: Reception > Public; Private > Private; Service > Service

Moderate Modern

After the II World War Modernism started a revision process where its dogmas were reviewed, formal aspects included. The ‘New Nordic Empiricism’ was the starting point, followed by the Italian ‘Neo-realism’. In this specific example, as it was said, the future dwellers were listened, in order to try to understand their needs and dreams. The main difference between the INA-Casa process and the Olivais Portuguese experience was the order of the process itself, since the inquiries to the population were made after the houses have been built. The consequence was that in Portugal many dwellers revealed to be dissatisfied (making the above mentioned alterations), while in Italy, far from being a consensual process, there were some constants among projects that proved, partially, that there was some consensus (like the need of a ‘lavoro’).

Unmeasured Modern

A small reference here to the Russian Constructivism, where the entire notion of the traditional house was destroyed, starting with its occupants, the traditional family. The Individual would be the main unit of the ‘shelter’ since all was defined according to the inexistence of any family ties. Communal spaces substituted the kitchen, the bathrooms; bedroom would be bigger in order to offer a private lounge space to its occupant, when the apartment was shared, in the ‘transition’ model from the traditional house to the final Dom-kommuna.

Figure 9: Dom-kommuna Narkomfin, 1927 (Moisei Ginzburg, 1892 - 1946)

The ‘House’ as a Shape: signs and symbols

The development of the idea of ‘social housing’, even before it was called this way, was based upon the urgent need to solve housing problems in the big cities where the Industrial Revolution had a strong presence. The migrating population left their houses in the country and flew to the city, where the homes they could afford were shared rooms resulting from speculation.

A political instrument

The previous life of the populations was far from being ideal, since their houses had no comfort at all, and famine was common, as agriculture started to decline. Even so, a bucolic image of a little hut in the countryside was starting to be built, as the complete opposite of the contemporary city.

Garden-cities were hardly ‘social housing’, but they were the first models to explore the idea of an urban settlement in harmony with nature. In Letchworth (1905) Geoffrey Lucas (1872-1947) referred that the houses were design in order to look like cottages rather than small houses⁶. This was a posture denied by Modern architects, like Mies Van der Rohe (1886-1969) who headed the Weissenhof Colony (1927). Numerous architects participated in order to show healthy new homes⁷. Their image was white, pure, Modern, the opposite of the previous example, and once empowered, the Nazi regime considered it intolerable. It promotes the isolated house with a ‘traditional’ sloped roof, as in Rottweil, a settlement built far away from the city centres. The benefits were double for the regime: the poorer were kept out of sight and people were supposed to be happy with their cottages.

Figure 10: Weissenhof, 1927 (Mies van der Rohe, 1886-1969) and Rottweil, 1937-1940 (...)

The Portuguese totalitarian regime of the ‘Estado Novo’ (‘New Estate’) also tried this path in their own proposal of social housing, with the ‘Casas Económicas’ (Economical Houses) 1918 project. The urban structure was still the bourgeois one, and in 1928, through the assumed influence of the Garden-Cities, single houses surrounded by a little garden typology was used to achieve that peaceful and bucolic character, proving that the process was ‘filled with a strong symbolism and an elaborate ideology’⁸.

The reference to an upraised social status is thus obvious in these experiments that we can assimilate, in most cases, to right-wing political thinking (Garden-cities excluded, of course). The basis of all these conceptions of a ‘single house for the poor’ was the traditional family, precisely what was put in to question by the Soviet Communists, who intended, as referred, a communitarian living in buildings conceived according to a beehive. Even so, the communist regime became suspicious of this ‘family revolution’, opting later for more ‘soothing’ solutions for the Russian dwellers. According to Bruno Zevi (quoted by Leonardo Benevolo) totalitarianism is always hostile to Modernism, since it admits free-will and self-determination, a menace to the established order or at least a question better not raised⁹.

⁶ www.tomorrowsgardencity.com/system/files/25_July_1905.pdf, [01.2009]

⁷ **Schoenauer, Norbert** – ‘6,000 Years of Housing, revised and expanded edition’, W. W. Norton & Company, New York, NY 10110, 2000; ISBN 0-393-73052-2

⁸ **Nunes, João Pedro Silva** - ‘Lisboa, arquitetura e urbanismo à escala humana: planeamento urbano e arquitetura de habitação em Olivais Sul, Lisboa 1959-1969’, 2007, Câmara Municipal de Lisboa, page 148, ISBN: 978-972-8543-08-2

⁹ **Benevolo, Leonardo** – ‘História da Arquitectura Moderna’, 2004, 3th edition – second reprint, Editora Perspectiva S. A.

Singular/Plural

We are used to think about the Modern Movement as a clean slate in architecture, and in its models we can hardly recognise the ‘house’ we’ve talking about. As this was considered inadequate, new types were proposed although nowadays we tend to think that the real dwellers (not as imagined by Modernists) were the real inadequate elements.

The house was the primal element of all Modernist Architecture, as there was a need to urgently respond to the housing shortage that derived into a stacking solution, instead of the isolated house. Efficiency and repetition become housing standards, neighbourhoods becoming a repetition of standardized cells. Ernst May (1886-1970), for instance, saw the city as a linear process based upon repetition¹⁰.

According to the ‘new’ city, that was idealized backwards (house > building > block > city), its growth was an inverse process, starting with the individual towards the collective. This was an attempt to overcome housing shortage, speculation and urgency.

However Modernist Architecture wasn’t that ‘cold’ or disconnected of the concept of the ‘primitive hut’, as the idea of the House was present in many proposal from Modernist Architects, even if disguised under their efficiency and novelty. Some extreme functionalists proposed a scientific approach that established almost mathematical proportions, in area, sunlight and air, according to the number of occupants of a determined cell. The most famous example was Alexander Klein (1879-1961), whose ‘cells’ for Bad Dürrenberg had variable area if one room was to be occupied by one or two dwellers.

Figure 11: Cells ‘C2’, ‘C7’, ‘C9’ and ‘C16’: for couples with one children, two children with separate rooms, two same sex children sharing a room and three or four children; the area of the lounge increases with the number of dwellers.

Unit/Multiple

The idea of repetition, even if the units were infinitely stacked or side-by-side, it can correspond to a definition of ‘house’, formal and anthropologically, where the dweller is able to recognize its ‘own’ house. Le Corbusier (1887-1965) produces an important investigation upon these principles, even if most of them remained pure experiments. The ‘Pavillon de l’Esprit Nouveau’ was conceived as temporary structure for the 1925 Paris’ Decorative Arts International Exhibition. Rather than a pavilion, it was a house, a duplex striped of ornament that served as well as manifest against the notion of ‘decorative arts’. Demolished after the exhibition, it served as a unit for the project, never built, of the ‘Immeuble-Villas’, where those duplex houses, with a private courtyard were stacked and joined side-by-side in order to compose a big housing building.

This project was no social housing building, but illustrates the house has a shape and a meaning in Corbusier’s thinking. In 1925 he finally manages to put together a neighbourhood destined to the workers of the Frugés Company, in Pessac. The ‘Quartier Moderne’ was composed by side-by-side houses (the

¹⁰ **Montaner, Josep Maria** – *‘Depois do Movimento Moderno: Arquitectura da segunda metade do séc. XX’* – Editorial Gustavo Gili, Barcelona, 2001, pág. 139, ISBN 84-252-1828-4

Modern compromise with House and Density), and it was based in a 5 by 5 meters cube upon which the traditional local houses were made. Besides his efforts, the use of a traditional construction process, rather than the idealized (but hard to put into practice) ‘projected’ concrete elevated the cost of the houses to a level that a worker hardly could sustain.

Figure 12: the ‘Pavillon de l’Esprit Nouveau’, the ‘Immeuble-Villas and the ‘Quartier Modern Frugés’

Street/House

The relation that is established between the street and the cell is something that cannot be set apart when thinking about a ‘house’. It’s a place for conviviality and community life, especially if the ‘inner cell’ is as small as it tends to be in social housing. The traditional European city, dense, vertical and clustered, wasn’t able to offer this kind of use of the street with quality or hygiene, but since the first planned city expansions a more open and useful outer space become part of the commission.

The Spangen Quarter (1919), from Michiel Brinkman (1873-1925), was one of the first examples to use the outside gallery not only as a mere entrance to the flats, but also as a space capable of supporting urban life. And, until today, remains one of the most successful. This ‘elevated street’ lies in the 2nd floor of the building, since the flats below have direct access to the ‘ground street’. The upper flats are duplexes so they can all have direct access to the gallery/street.

Over the time there have been many examples of these streets in the air, but their failure was due to a question of scale, that is mastered in Spangen: the gallery has a width between 2,2 and 3,3 meters and it’s only two floors away from the ground. Apart from this there were also elevators that made possible to the milkman and the baker to deliver milk and bread as in any ground floor. Therefore the identification of a ‘house’ occurs not only when each entrance accesses the flat directly from the street, but also because these ‘streets’, real or virtual, are defined as such by the kind of urban living it supports.

Figure 13: The Spangen Quarter: the galleries and the ‘cells’ (ground/first floor; second/third floor)

Although the top floors have duplexes, in the flats below Brinkman chooses to overlay single-floor flats, although the top one as a private stair directly from the ground. Despite being a miscellaneous solution between the traditional ‘horizontal street’ and the very Modern’ vertical street’, it proves wrong Keneth

Frampton when he states that vertical streets never were an effective solution compared to the ones in the ground¹¹.

House/Street

After the 2nd World War the urban solutions reviewed completely the traditional city, abandoning the elements that had been defining it throughout the centuries: the street, the plot or the block. Buildings became out of scale, as a result of an almost infinite stacking of individual cells served by communal daycares, washrooms or even stores. Even if the duplex and the gallery are inherited from previous experiments, the ‘house’ becomes undoubtedly the starting point of the ‘new’ settlements. Le Corbusier’s ‘Unités d’Habitation’ are known as the main example of this new urban attitude, mainly the one in Marseille (1947-1953), although there are others: Nantes (1955), Berlin (1958), Briey-la-Forêt (1963) or Firminy (1965), these being, perhaps, more interesting for us since their units were smaller, for example.

Figure 14: Unité d’Habitation in Briey-la-Forêt (1963): section, juxtaposition of cells and photo

As a result of the ‘L-shaped’ living cell, conceived as bottle supported by a cellaret (the structure) the street becomes an inner-corridor supposed to support urban life. As for the cell, the attempt was to recreate a house, a three-bedroom duplex for a ‘normal’ family. The living-room has a double-height ceiling (partially), with a balcony which was intended to be an outdoor extension of the cell, just like in a ‘house’: the façade of the flat was a two-storey residence...

House/Building

This kind of solution for the façade is very important for the identification of ‘my house’ among the other cells. In the previous example the cells remained rather anonymous, due to the whole scale of the building, but in 1952 Chamberlin, Powell e Bon¹² conceived a whole estate just in the middle of London that ‘solved the problem’. In an area devastated by war, a truly ‘Modern’ urban layout was juxtaposed to a traditional fabric, but in an attempt to dialogue with the surroundings, buildings were smaller, ‘shorter’, more human, if we prefer. The layout of the cell is very similar to the one in the ‘Unités d’Habitation’, despite occupying just one ‘side’ of the gallery (which became open). The living-room balcony was double-heightened so the above bedroom would lean over it. As the balcony was ‘closed’ sideways, the dweller, from his bedroom or lounge, only saw his house’s outer space. ‘My house’ became identifiable from the inside and the outside.

¹¹ Frampton, Keneth – ‘Historia critica de la arquitectura moderna’ - Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. 08029 Barcelona, 1996, pág. 273, ISBN 84-252-1628-1

¹² 1920 – 1999 (Geoffrey Chamberlin); 1919 – 1978 (Peter ‘Joe’ Powell); 1919 – 1978 (Christoph Bon)

Figure 15: Golden Lane Estate (1952): rear façade (gallery and bedrooms), front façade (with the double-height balcony) and typical cell.

As a proof of the success of the whole housing complex, dwellers have an internet site¹³ where they invite all dwellers to publish their photo in order to recognize them as neighbours and discuss problems and solutions for the complex. A kind of pride also found in Ernst May's (1886-1970) Praunheim (1927) where the author is recognized and his drawings published in their site¹⁴.

Building/Maze

The main element that differentiates the previous examples is thus the scale of the complex, as in the promotion of a 'sense of belonging' (and not as an evaluation of the whole architectural project). The use of solutions as the duplex, the open gallery and such cannot overcome reality, even if theory tries to defend any gallery as a 'street in the sky'. The 'Robin Hood Gardens' project (1972), from Alison (1928-1993) and Peter Smithson (1923-2003) tried to encourage a review of Modernism's urban dogmas, arguing that they promoted anonymous and sterile cities. The cells were one floor and two floors solutions (upwards and downwards) in an attempt to converge as many doors as possible to the gallery. The cell's entrances were positioned in 'niches' in the gallery so neighbours could meet at their doorsteps talking and saying their hellos.

Nevertheless, the anonymity of the whole building and its galleries, which all looked the same with no special features that qualified them as 'my street' where 'my house' is, condemned the architects' intentions: as a solution, it became not much different from another supposedly Modern buildings (plenty of proposals we see in our suburbs are mere misrepresentations of Modernism's intentions).

Figure 16: 'Robin Hood Gardens' (1972): the building and its galleries.

House/House

The fall of the totalitarian regime in Portugal creates the opportunity to express political alternatives to fascism, but also to try out architectural experiments that were forbidden by the 'Português Suave' ('Mild Portuguese Style') defended by the regime. In 1974 the references were no longer Modern ones, even less

¹³ <http://www.goldenlaneestate.org/>, [09.2010]

¹⁴ <http://www.siedlerverein.de/>, [09.2010]

the soviet Constructivism. The INA-Casa in Italy was taken into account, since its purposes fitted the Portuguese needs: suppress housing shortage, to promote construction and create jobs. The use of common labour to build with traditional techniques helped in every aspect, and in Portugal dwellers were even supposed to help to build their own homes.

The inquiries made to the population, inherited from the INA-Casa but also considered necessary after the partial success of Olivais, due to the ‘resistance’ to Modern solutions (kitchens, dining-rooms...). Nevertheless, between the north and the south of Portugal different aspirations were listened, according to the models that the future dwellers had, even if the political/practical program (the above mentioned SAAL) was the same.

The architects also played an important role in this process, and up North there was the consensus among designers that the traditional city needed mending, since the pre-existing spatial and social order seemed convenient: the attempt was to keep populations in their context, the city, not a suburb. The ‘house’ becomes the base-unit of the projects of, for example, Álvaro Siza, perhaps still a Modern idea, but that was adapted to the surrounding scale: the row-houses in ‘Bairro de São Victor’ (1976) reveals influences from the Modernist projects of Oud or Taut¹⁵ and corresponds to an economical way to give dwellers ‘a house’.

Figure 17: ‘São Victor’ neighbourhood, 1976

The need to establish a closer dialogue with its surroundings in the ‘Bairro da Bouça’, who were higher, for instance, than in ‘São Victor’, defines a four-storey building, but even here the main unit is still the cell, or the house: the building is like the overlap of two rows of houses, duplexes with a direct access to the ground floor or to a gallery in the upper row.

Figure 18: ‘Bouça’ neighbourhood: the 1977 project, revised internally in 2004 when the construction was completed.

¹⁵ Costa, Alexandre Alves quoted by **Bandeirinha, José António** – “O processo SAAL e a arquitectura no 25 de Abril de 1974”, 2007, Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra, page 219, ISBN: 978-972-8704-76-6

Figure 19: 'Bouça' neighbourhood, 2004, after completion/renovation.

The upper gallery, very narrow, as no use as a cell's outdoor space, or even as a meeting spot. In one hand, we can consider that as a flaw, since offering more outside space, especially in social housing, is always a plus, as people are not obliged to make use of it. On the other hand, in 1977 Siza Vieira had already realized how utopian the 'streets in the sky' were, preferring to design a simple outside corridor. And again, in Portuguese culture, privacy is very dear to dwellers and the option was to offer patios inside the house's perimeter. This was one of the aspects that were redefined in 2004, since most dwellers closed those patios in search of some extra area. And their conversions were acknowledged and adapted to new blocks that completed the whole project.

Conclusion

The attempt to make any house a home has many different characters, since it derives from one's culture but also from the previous living experiences. Insalubrity and degradation don't define for themselves the desire for any kind of house, but in one which complies with the dwellers' expectations in social representation.

As architecture in general gave up trying to change the (whole) world and started to pay attention to actual needs and a changing society (rather than respond to an intended society), models started to be created taking into account social and sociability needs, rather than just being functional.

Nevertheless the previous efforts weren't inglorious, as the house as a unit was an explored theme in every type of dwelling. We must take into account that it is not always possible to build with low density, since a tight budget almost always means exactly that: density. And as we observe a mere duplex in a high rise building we must have in mind that this kind of 'homeliness' wasn't spontaneous but a result of an intense investigation and experiment.

Figures

Fig. 1: **Sindicato Nacional dos Arquitectos** – *'Arquitectura Popular em Portugal'*, 4ª edição, 2004, ISBN 972-97668-7-8

Fig. 2: Author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner** – *'Viviendas en bloques alineados'*, 1992, Barcelona, Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A., ISBN: 968-887-186-9

Fig. 3: Author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **Câmara Municipal de Lisboa**, Outubro 1967 – *'Habitação Social na cidade de Lisboa, 1959-1966'*

Fig. 4: Author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **Câmara Municipal de Lisboa**, Outubro 1967 – *'Habitação Social na cidade de Lisboa, 1959-1966'*

Fig. 5: Author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **Costa, João Pedro** – *'Bairro de Alvalade – um paradigma no urbanismo português'*, Livros Horizonte/Faculdade de Arquitectura da UTL, 2ª edição 2005, ISBN 972-24-1382-4;

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Fig. 8: Author's drawings.

Fig. 9: Author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **French, Hilary** - *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, 2008 Laurence King Publishing Ltd, ISBN-13: 978-1-85669-564-0; <http://teoriarquitectura.blogspot.com/2009/06/bloco-como-paradigma-moderno.html>, [04.2010]

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